

Magnetic Dipole Localization With a Gradiometer: Obtaining Unique Solutions

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Abstract--The five independent equations describing the field gradient tensor at a point for a static magnetic dipole source can be inverted to give the bearing vector to the source and the source moment vector divided by the fourth power of the range. The equations have four solutions, two of which are related in a non-trivial way, and two more that are obtained by reflections through the field point. The symmetry of the four solutions in the principal-axis frame of the gradient tensor can be used to express the solutions directly in terms of one another in an arbitrary frame without executing the inversion. This relationship has been exploited to construct explicit proofs that a unique solution for magnetic moment vector and relative position between source and field point can be obtained if either the magnetic field vector, or the rate of change of the gradient tensor and the relative motion of source and field point is known.

arrangement in the plane, defined by \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{r} , which forms a coordinate plane in the gradient tensor's principal-axis system. This arrangement is shown in Fig.1. These solutions can be expressed directly in terms of one another in an arbitrary frame without executing the inversion [3]. If we physically generate the gradient tensor with the scaled moment \mathbf{M} and bearing vector \mathbf{n} , then solutions for scaled moment \mathbf{R} and bearing vector \mathbf{u} not trivially related to the input scaled moment and bearing vector are given by

$$\mathbf{R} = \pm \frac{[10(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 - 2M^2]\mathbf{n} - 5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})\mathbf{M}}{\sqrt{4M^2 + 5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2}}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \pm \frac{5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})\mathbf{n} - 2\mathbf{M}}{\sqrt{4M^2 + 5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2}}, \quad (5)$$

INTRODUCTION

For a magnetic dipole source of moment \mathbf{m} located at the origin, the magnetic field \mathbf{b} at a point located at \mathbf{r} is given by

$$\mathbf{b} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \left[\frac{3(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{r})\mathbf{r}}{r^5} - \frac{\mathbf{m}}{r^3} \right] \quad (1)$$

and the gradient tensor has the form

$$G_{ij} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \left[-\frac{15(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{r})r_i r_j}{r^7} + \frac{3m_i r_j}{r^5} + \frac{3m_j r_i}{r^5} + \frac{3(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{r})\delta_{ij}}{r^5} \right] \quad (2)$$

which, with the introduction of the bearing vector $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{r}/r$ and the scaled moment vector $\mathbf{M} = 3\mu_0\mathbf{m}/(4\pi r^4)$, can be expressed as

$$G_{ij} = -5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})n_i n_j + M_i n_j + M_j n_i + (\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})\delta_{ij}. \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) has five unknowns, and there are five independent elements of the gradient tensor, since $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{b} = 0$, and $\nabla \times \mathbf{b} = 0$ for static magnetic sources in nonmagnetic media. Equation (3) has been inverted [1], and the details can be found in the references cited therein, or in [2]. There are four solutions for \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{n} and they have a symmetric

with identical expressions giving \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{n} in terms of \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{u} .

The bearing vectors \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{n} will lie in the same half-space ($\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{n} \geq 0$) if we choose the positive sign in (4) and (5) when $\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n} \geq 0$ and the negative sign otherwise. We will refer to the solution for \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{u} selected this way as the "ghost" solution. Equations (4) and (5) are essential to the uniqueness proofs to be developed below

UNIQUENESS PROOF: KNOWN FIELD VECTOR

Expressed in terms of the scaled moment \mathbf{M} and bearing vector \mathbf{n} , (1) becomes

$$\mathbf{b} = r \left[(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})\mathbf{n} - \frac{\mathbf{M}}{3} \right]. \quad (6)$$

By inspection, if \mathbf{M}, \mathbf{n} is a solution of (3) that satisfies (6), then $-\mathbf{M}, -\mathbf{n}$ cannot satisfy (6), and the number of acceptable solutions of (3) has been reduced from four to two. Next, we will assume that \mathbf{M}, \mathbf{n} satisfies (3) and (6), and ask if the "ghost" solution \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{u} defined by (4) and (5) can also satisfy (6), possibly with a different range \hat{r} . That is, can we satisfy

$$r \left[(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})\mathbf{n} - \frac{\mathbf{M}}{3} \right] = \hat{r} \left[(\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{u})\mathbf{u} - \frac{\mathbf{R}}{3} \right] \quad (7)$$

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Figure 1. Principal-Axis Frame Solution Arrangement.

with \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{u} given by (4) and (5)? If we square both sides of (7) we get

$$r^2[3(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 - M^2] = \hat{r}^2[3(\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{u})^2 - R^2]. \quad (8)$$

However, we know [3] that $(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 = (\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{u})^2$ and $M^2 = R^2$ so we conclude $\hat{r} = r$. Thus, we attempt to satisfy (7) with the range factor removed. Equations (4) and (5) are valid in any reference frame and this means that upon substitution in (7), the resulting scalar coefficients of the vectors on the two sides of the equation must be identical. In particular, for the coefficient of \mathbf{M} we get the equation

$$\frac{(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})}{\sqrt{5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 + 4M^2}} = 1 \Rightarrow (\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 + M^2 = 0, \quad (9)$$

which is unphysical. Consequently, we conclude that the solution \mathbf{M}, \mathbf{n} common to (3) and (6) is unique, and the two together lead to a solution for r via (6) and a thus a unique solution for \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{r} .

GRADIENT RATE TENSOR

When there is relative motion between the field measurement point and the dipole source, a tensor gradiometer can be used to measure the rate of change of the gradient tensor, which we will refer to simply as the rate tensor. Taking the time derivative of (2) gives

$$R_{ij} = \frac{dG_{ij}}{dt} = \mathbf{v} \frac{dG_{ij}}{ds} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \left[\frac{105(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{r})(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{r})r_i r_j}{r^9} - \frac{15(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{v})r_i r_j}{r^7} - \frac{15(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{r})v_i r_j}{r^7} - \frac{15(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{r})v_j r_i}{r^7} - \frac{15(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{r})m_i r_j}{r^7} - \frac{15(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{r})m_j r_i}{r^7} - \frac{15(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{r})(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{r})\delta_{ij}}{r^7} + \frac{3m_i v_j}{r^5} + \frac{3m_j v_i}{r^5} + \frac{3(\mathbf{m} \cdot \mathbf{v})\delta_{ij}}{r^5} \right], \quad (10)$$

where we have shown two forms, a time derivative, and, via the chain rule, a spatial derivative along the path of motion of the field point. The first form is useful for a stationary source and a field point of known velocity, such as in localization from air borne or water borne platforms. The second form is useful when the field measurements are sampled along a line in space without regard to speed, such as in a survey mode seeking buried objects. In this latter case, the speed can be factored from (10) and only the direction of relative motion matters. Equation (10) has been inverted [4] to give solutions for bearing vector and the moment vector scaled by the fifth power of the range. That process produces multiple solutions, and previous numerical work indicates that the solution common to the new inversion and the gradient tensor inversion is unique. The present work establishes a unique solution rigorously, and does so without inversion of the gradient rate equations.

In terms of the scaled moment vector and the bearing vector, the rate equations can be written in the form

$$R_{ij} = \frac{1}{r} [35(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n})n_i n_j - 5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{v})n_i n_j - 5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})v_i n_j - 5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})v_j n_i - 5(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n})M_i n_j - 5(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n})M_j n_i - 5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})(\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n})\delta_{ij} + M_i v_j + M_j v_i + (\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{v})\delta_{ij}], \quad (11)$$

In the following, we will interpret \mathbf{v} to be the field point velocity when R_{ij} is the time rate tensor, and a unit vector in the direction of field point translation when R_{ij} represents the along-track space rate of change.

UNIQUENESS PROOF: KNOWN RATE TENSOR

We assume that \mathbf{v} is specified, and that \mathbf{M}, \mathbf{n} is a solution of (3) that satisfies (11). By inspection of (11), $-\mathbf{M}, -\mathbf{n}$ cannot be a solution, so the number of possible solutions satisfying (3) and (11) is at most two. Next, we assume that the "ghost" solution given by (4) and (5) satisfies (11), possibly for a different range \hat{r} . We substitute \mathbf{R}, \mathbf{u} from (4) and (5) into (11) and expand, and equate the resulting expression to the explicit form in (11). We will not write this expression out, but will just examine selected terms. Again, rotational invariance is invoked, and in the resulting expression, coefficients of specific elementary tensors on both sides of the equation must be identical. In particular, for the coefficient of $M_i v_j + M_j v_i$ we get the equation

$$\frac{5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})}{\hat{r} \sqrt{5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 + 4M^2}} = \frac{1}{r}, \quad (12)$$

and for the coefficient of $n_i v_j + n_j v_i$ we get

$$\frac{25(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 + 2M^2}{\hat{r}\sqrt{5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 + 4M^2}} = \frac{5(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})}{r}, \quad (13)$$

and when we combine (12) and (13) we conclude $M^2 = 0$, which is unphysical. Consequently, we conclude that the solution of (3) that satisfies (11) for specified \mathbf{v} is unique. It remains now to use the rate tensor to perform the scaling to obtain moment and position vectors.

EXPLOITING THE RATE TENSOR

Equation (11) can be written in tensor form (summation convention) as

$$R_{ij} = \frac{1}{r} Q_{ijk} v_k \Rightarrow \frac{v_k}{r} = \tilde{Q}_{ijk} R_{ij} \quad (14)$$

where Q_{ijk} is mathematically similar to the tensor T_{ijk} appearing in the direct inversion of the gradient rate equations [4], with \mathbf{M} replacing \mathbf{v} in the latter expression. Consequently, we can immediately write the inverse tensor \tilde{Q}_{ijk} as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{Q}_{ijk} = & \frac{M^2(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2}{[M^4 - (\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^4]} n_i n_j n_k \\ & - \frac{3(\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2 + 5M^2}{8[M^4 - (\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^4]} (M_i n_j + M_j n_i) n_k \\ & + \frac{1}{2[M^2 - (\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})^2]} [n_i n_j M_k \\ & - (\mathbf{M} \cdot \mathbf{n})(\delta_{ik} n_j + \delta_{jk} n_i) + \delta_{ik} M_j + \delta_{jk} M_i]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Given the prescribed platform motion \mathbf{v} , the rate tensor R_{ij} , and either expression in (14), the range r can be determined, and \mathbf{m} and \mathbf{r} are uniquely determined. We have included this last step (15) to provide the basis for further analysis of the gradient-gradient rate inversion procedure when the relative motion of field point and source is not known *a priori*. This will be the topic of a future paper.

CONCLUSION AND COMMENTS

Given the gradient tensor at a point due to a magnetic dipole source, knowledge of either the field vector at the

same point, or the gradient rate tensor at the same point along with the relative motion of source and field point, leads to a unique solution for the relative position of source and measurement point and the magnetic moment vector of the source. In practice, due to the large background magnetic field of the earth, the field vector due to a source can be used only when the measuring device is stationary, so this mode only has utility in, say, tracking a moving magnetic source with a fixed sensor. However, for this case, no *a priori* knowledge of the relative motion of source and sensor is needed. For mobile sensor applications, the gradient and gradient rate tensors appear to be the only practical candidates for point-by-point dipole localization, and this process as we have described it above requires precise knowledge of the motion of the sensor relative to the source. Consequently, the two cases we have described are complementary, and both have useful applications.

As a final practical note, the uniqueness proofs do not constitute prescriptions for obtaining the unique solution. In practice, all four gradient tensor solutions (two if the source halfspace is known) must be tested to see which produces the associated field vector or gradient rate tensor.

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